

Lanthanide Contraction-Driven Modulation of Photoswitchable Macrocyclic Complexes Reveals Unprecedented Glass-Induced Re-isomerization and Luminescent Thermometry

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Designing light-responsive supramolecular architectures with lanthanide ions offers a promising route towards multifunctional materials with tunable photophysical properties. Here, we report a systematic investigation across the lanthanide series of macrocyclic complexes incorporating azobenzene-functionalized diaza-crown ether ligands. We show that subtle changes in ionic radius across the Ln³⁺ series dictate conformational preferences and modulate *trans*-to-*cis* photoisomerization efficiency under UV and visible light. Surprisingly, we uncover that the reverse *cis*-to-*trans* isomerization, which is here unresponsive to thermal or photonic stimuli, is uniquely triggered by contact with glass surfaces, revealing a previously overlooked route for controlling molecular photoswitching. Additionally, selected complexes display efficient visible and near-infrared emission leveraged for robust luminescent thermometric behaviour in the solid state, with tunable sensitivity linked to the lanthanide. These findings advance the field of light-driven supramolecular materials and demonstrate how careful molecular-level design of lanthanide–azobenzene assemblies enables control over photoswitching, luminescence and thermal sensing properties, highlighting glass-mediated re-isomerization as a novel phenomenon with implications for future photoresponsive materials.

1. Introduction

Light is a fundamental source of energy in photosynthesis, and harnessing light-matter interactions through artificial molecular systems opens pathways towards energy conversion and information processing at the molecular level. The design and synthesis of novel light-responsive supramolecular architectures are therefore of great importance for the development of smart, stimuli-responsive functional materials.^{1,2} Advancing our understanding of these interactions through the engineering of new materials is a key scientific direction, with potential applications including electronic and optical devices,^{3,4} data storage,⁵⁻⁷ biological imaging, medical diagnostics, targeted drug delivery,^{8,9} sensing,^{10,11} encryption,¹² anti-counterfeiting technologies or multicolour QR codes.^{1,13,14}

There is a growing interest in the development of macrocyclic systems functionalized with photoswitchable units, as light offers a non-invasive and highly tunable stimulus for dynamic control over molecular conformation and properties in supramolecular assemblies.^{15,16} Among the most widely used photoresponsive motifs is azobenzene, which undergoes reversible photoisomerization between two different geometric isomers – a linear *trans*-form and a bent *cis*-form –

enabling modulation of supramolecular photophysical behaviour.^{13, 17, 18} Many light-responsive macrocycles incorporating azobenzene have been reported, though predominantly in metal-free systems.¹⁹⁻²⁵ When metal ions are introduced, coordination can either quench the photoswitching activity²⁶ or, conversely, enhance the selectivity, accelerate and improve control of the photoswitching processes.²⁷ These demonstrate a crucial role of matching energy levels and photochromic units to achieve effective and tunable photoswitchable behaviour.

Recent studies have highlighted the impact of transition metal ions in expanding the functionality of light-responsive systems, enabling properties that are otherwise unattainable in purely organic frameworks.^{28, 29} In particular, integrating luminescent lanthanide ions with light-responsive molecules has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance both emission and photoswitching behaviour.^{26, 30-32} Switchable lanthanide complexes align well with the concept of multi-stimuli-responsive architectures, exhibiting sensitivity to light, but also to chemical, thermal, electrical or mechanical inputs. This multifunctionality makes such materials increasingly desirable for applications in chemical sensing, cellular imaging, security tagging, and, most recently, as advanced luminescent optical thermometers.^{12, 33-36} In *d*-block systems, temperature shifts the balance between ligand- and metal-centered excited states and their nonradiative decay, with ratiometric intensity or lifetime being the thermometric readout (e.g. Re₂-L anions bridged with diamine-organic linkers³⁷ or [Bz₂NH₂]₂[Mn(OC₆F₅)₄] ionic assembly³⁸). In *f*-block complexes, the response often follows redistribution among crystal-field *m_J* sublevels and thermally

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Figure 1. An overview of key concepts present in this work, which demonstrate the photoactive Ln-macrocyclic complexes in the context of lanthanide contraction.

assisted antenna-4f energy transfer, enabling self-calibrated intensity ratios, lifetimes or band-shape changes. Examples include a self-calibrated Dy^{3+} thermometer that also shows single-ion magnet (SIM) behaviour³⁹ or dinuclear single-molecule magnet (SMM) Nd^{3+} platforms linking ligation to thermometric performance.⁴⁰ Independent magneto-optical readouts can further improve thermal sensitivity.⁴¹ Macrocyclic ligand designs further highlight multifunctionality: Y^{3+} -diluted Dy^{3+} complex acts as a bifunctional SIM and luminescent thermometer, with both functions active below its blocking temperature⁴², and our Nd^{3+} macrocyclic SIM operates as a temperature-independent manometer and pressure-independent thermometer.⁴³ These precedents motivate the photoswitchable $\text{Nd}^{3+}/\text{Yb}^{3+}$ macrocyclic complexes studied here and frame our analysis of how lanthanide contraction shape their near-infrared thermometric response.

A number of azobenzene-functionalized lanthanide complexes have been reported to date, their photoisomerization behaviour and structure-function relationships remain under active investigation.^{44–53} However, comprehensive studies encompassing a broad range of lanthanide ions with organic ligands are still rare, limiting a deeper understanding of lanthanide contraction effects and their influence on structure and functionality in photoresponsive systems. Although lanthanide–macrocyclic complexes have been widely studied in fields such as biomedical imaging,^{54, 55} antenna-based emission systems,^{55, 56} and molecular nanomagnets (SMMs/SIMs),^{55, 57} the integration of photoswitchable units into such systems remains extremely limited. Lariat-type macrocycles bearing azobenzene moieties have primarily been developed for s-block metal ion

coordination or membrane-mimetic applications²⁴, while analogous systems with lanthanides are exceedingly rare.

In this work, we present a systematic study on the diaza-crown ether macrocycle functionalized with azobenzene units **L-AzoH₂**, forming a distinct class of lanthanide complexes designed to investigate the structural and photophysical effects of lanthanide contraction. Despite the common quenching of azobenzene switching by metal coordination, our system retains efficient light-induced isomerization while exhibiting a high stability of the *cis*-form—reverting to the *trans*-isomer unusually fast under contact with the glass surface. Finally, representative complexes from both the *syn*- and *anti*-conformational families were evaluated as luminescent thermometers, establishing a novel correlation between macrocyclic geometry, switching behaviour and near-infrared emissive sensing across the lanthanide series (Figure 1).

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Choice of the ligand, synthesis and characterization

Diaza-crown ether macrocyclic ligand was chosen as: 1) macrocycles with N_2O_4 coordination cavity form stable lanthanide complexes; and 2) allow symmetric functionalization with different groups, which should tune the photoresponsive properties. A pendant-arm azobenzene macrocyclic ligand named **L-AzoH₂** was obtained through the Mannich reaction, based on a previously reported procedure⁵⁸ with a slight modification of purification method (Section 1.3 in SI). The purity and homogeneity was confirmed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), electrospray mass spectrometry (ESI-MS), nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) (Figures S1–S7).

Figure 2. Scheme for the synthesis of macrocyclic complexes with included conformations of the L-AzoH₂ ligand scaffold.

2.2. Design, synthesis and characterization of complexes

To understand the influence of interactions between the metal centers and the ligand molecule for development of stimuli responsive azobenzene systems, we focused on the synthesis and investigation of compounds with lanthanide ions, interesting for their emissive properties. To better understand the role of deprotonation of the ligand for photoresponsivity, neutral CuL-Azo system was also obtained. Simple complex with a sodium ion - [NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃, and an uncoordinated ligand L-AzoH₂ molecule were also used as references. [NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃ complex was synthesized in an acetonitrile solution by the complexation reaction of the NaCF₃SO₃ salt with the L-AzoH₂ ligand. Cu²⁺ and Ln³⁺ complexes were synthesized in similar manner, in an acetonitrile (CuL-Azo) or acetonitrile/methanol (LnL-AzoCF₃SO₃) mixture (1:1, v:v) by the complexation reaction of the corresponding triflate salts with the L-AzoH₂ ligand in the presence of triethylamine (Et₃N), used as a deprotonating agent (Figure 2). A detailed description of the synthesis, isolation, spectroscopy and solid-state characterization of the complexes can be found in the supplementary information (Sections 1.4. and 1.5.). FT-IR spectra (Figures S8-S12) of lanthanide complexes from La³⁺ to Lu³⁺ are almost identical which confirmed high isostructurality in the solid state. This is also consistent with mass spectra of these assemblies, as the peaks observed in the positive mode of the ESI-MS spectra indicate the formation of mononuclear complexes containing one L-Azo ligand molecule with two deprotonated OH groups from azobenzene pendant-arms of the macrocycle for all complexes (Figures S13-S24).

2.2.1. Single crystal and powder X-ray Crystallography

Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction studies were obtained by slow evaporation from dimethyl sulfoxide solution for L-AzoH₂ ligand, by slow diffusion of diisopropyl ether into

solution of chloroform (CuL-Azo) or acetonitrile/dichloromethane for lanthanide complexes LnL-AzoCF₃SO₃ and by slow diffusion of diisopropyl ether into solution of acetonitrile for the [NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃ complex. For sodium complex, two types of monocystals were obtained under identical conditions and exhibited different space groups. Therefore, both structures were solved for comparison and designated as forms A and B, respectively.

Figure 3 shows the comparison of the crystal structure of free L-AzoH₂ ligand molecule (a), its complex with sodium ion with non-deprotonated ligand (b) and complex with Cu²⁺ with deprotonated ligand form (c); molecular structure for the lanthanide complex in the *syn*-conformation (d) and packing diagram (e) of LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃ complex. The ligand molecule is C_i-symmetrical in the crystal structure, lying across the center of inversion in the space group P2₁/c (Figure 3a). The conformation of the macrocycle changes significantly upon complexation (Figure 3b-d), the change directs all N and O atoms towards the center of the complex. For the sodium complexes [NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃ (A and B), which are observed in both forms of different space group symmetry, CF₃SO₃⁻ acts as a counterion and is not coordinated to the central metal ion. Coordination number of the sodium cation is in both cases 8 (N₂O₆), and the crystal lattices contain space which is filled by more (B) or less (A) ordered solvent molecules (Figure 3b and Figure S25). Figure 3c shows neutral CuL-Azo complex, which is also centrosymmetric (C_i) with the Cu²⁺ ion located on an inversion centre. The metal ion is six-coordinate and is best described as a Jahn–Teller–elongated octahedron (4+2): four donors define a nearly square equatorial plane, while two much longer axial Cu⋯O contacts complete the coordination sphere (see Table S4). Such pronounced axial elongation is typical for d⁹ Cu²⁺ and is well preceded with over 4,000 six-coordinate Cu²⁺ entries in the CSD display comparably unequal axial Cu–O distances.

Figure 3. Crystal structures of: a) **L-AzoH₂** ligand; b) **[NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃ (A)** complex; c) **CuL-Azo** complex; d) **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complex; e) packing diagram of **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complex.

Determined crystal structures for **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **PrL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **SmL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **EuL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **GdL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **TbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **ErL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complexes have established that all Ln-assemblies are highly isostructural (Figure 3d,e and Figures S26–S32). They crystallize in the same space group ($P2_1/c$) and with very similar disposition of molecules in the crystal structure. The isostructurality goes so far that even the similar disorder of one of the dinitrogen bridges is found in all the structures. The lanthanide ion is 9-coordinated (quite typically) by two nitrogen and six oxygen atoms from the ligand molecule, four oxygen atoms from the macrocyclic ring and two oxygen atoms from the phenol moiety of the azobenzene pendant-arms, which are positioned at the same side of the macrocyclic unit resulting in a *syn* conformation. The coordination sphere is filled additionally by one oxygen atom from the coordinated triflate anion positioned at the opposite side of two azobenzene pendant-arms of macrocycle. We have recently demonstrated the crucial effect of a disordered triflate in the Nd^{3+} -macrocyclic assemblies for implementation of multifunctional characteristics.⁴³ Crystal data, data collection, structure refinement and geometrical characteristics for ligand and complexes are given in Tables S1–S4. The lanthanide contraction in the synthesized Ln-complexes influences the Ln–N and Ln–O bond distances, resulting in a general trend of gradual shortening of these bonds across the lanthanide series, with some exceptions to the expected trend (Table S4).

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns for **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **PrL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **SmL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **EuL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **GdL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **TbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **ErL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complexes also confirmed their isostructurality. Experimental

powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns of the lanthanide complexes were in accordance with simulated PXRD patterns based on single crystal diffraction data, indicating phase purity (Figure S33). The differences in the sharpness and narrowness of the corresponding PXRD signals are due to the poor crystallinity of the powdered samples. In the case of the **DyL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **HoL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **LuL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complexes obtained samples are not in the crystalline state, but in the amorphous phase, so their PXRD patterns were not possible to determine, but the experimental characterization confirm their purity and uniformity (see Section 1.5).

2.2.2. ¹H NMR spectroscopy

The **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **LuL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complexes were characterized using NMR spectroscopy (¹H, ¹³C, and 2D NMR: COSY and HSQC) in CDCl₃ (Figures S34–S41). The ¹H NMR spectra show significant differences from the free **L-AzoH₂** ligand, in both aromatic and aliphatic regions, indicating coordination of the lanthanide ions through donor atoms of the macrocycle and azobenzene arms (Figure 4). Both La^{3+} and Lu^{3+} complexes exist as single species in solution. The ¹H NMR spectrum of the La^{3+} complex is symmetric, indicating that the protons on both sides of the crown ether are chemically equivalent. This observation is consistent with X-ray crystallographic data, which show that the La^{3+} ion is centrally positioned within the macrocycle. In this complex, the azobenzene arms adopt a *syn*-conformation (both on the same side of the ring). In contrast, the Na^+ complex adopts an *anti*-conformation (arms on opposite sides), while also featuring a centrally located metal ion. Broad signals in the aliphatic region of the ¹H NMR spectra for both the La^{3+} and Na^+ complexes are

Figure 4. Stacked ^1H NMR spectra for **L-Azo** (black), $[\text{NaL-AzoH}_2]\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3$ (violet), $\text{LaL-AzoCF}_3\text{SO}_3$ (blue) and $\text{LuL-AzoCF}_3\text{SO}_3$ (green), with representation of coordination around cations.

likely due to fast dynamic exchange processes. The Lu^{3+} complex shows an asymmetric ^1H NMR pattern, indicating a distinct structure. The smaller Lu^{3+} ion, due to lanthanide contraction, is likely coordinated asymmetrically and displaced from the macrocycle center (see Section 2.4). The reorganization of the coordination environment around larger and smaller lanthanide ions and distinct conformational preferences in solution are recognized in the literature.^{59–64}

Beside different conformation of macrocycle cavity around the Ln centre in La^{3+} and Lu^{3+} assemblies, we suppose that the arrangement of coordinated azobenzene pendant-arms is also different. Firstly, the benzylic hydrogen resonances (methylene groups linking the crown moiety and azobenzene pendant-arms) differ between La^{3+} and Lu^{3+} complexes. These protons are a broad singlet in the La^{3+} , while in the Lu^{3+} they show a typical AX ($\delta_1 = 4.60$ ppm; $\delta_2 = 3.35$ ppm; $J = 12.6$ Hz; Spectrometer frequency = 600 MHz; $\Delta\nu/J \sim 60$) spin system and resonate as doublets of doublets with significantly different chemical shifts. It indicates that benzylic protons are diastereotopic thanks to the different chemical environment. This result, together with the difference of the crown-ether signals, indicates that the latter complex is more rigid on the NMR timescale. Moreover, comparing the aromatic region, we can see that chemical shifts in the Lu^{3+} are more closely related to the ligand, where from the crystal structure data determination we observe that azobenzene pendant-arms are preorganized at the two opposite sides of macrocyclic ligand skeleton (Figure 3a). Integration of all these results allows us to

predict that the azobenzene pendant arms adopt an *anti*-conformation in the Lu^{3+} complex. This is accompanied by a closely coordinated triflate anion near the Lu^{3+} center, which helps explain the observed conformational differences in solution. Comparison of energetic profiles via Density Functional Theory (DFT) studies also support the proposed *anti*-conformation in the $\text{LuL-AzoCF}_3\text{SO}_3$ complex (see Section 2.4).

2.3. Photoisomerization studies

2.3.1. *Trans*-to-*cis* isomerization

Due to the distinct shape and properties of the azobenzene molecule in its *trans*- and *cis*-forms, the characteristic absorption bands ($\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$) for these two states of the molecules make them detectable.¹ The photoisomerization properties of the synthesized compounds were studied in chloroform solution and monitored by UV-vis absorption spectroscopy. Typically, *trans*-to-*cis* photoisomerization of the azobenzene moiety is induced by UV or visible light irradiation.^{24, 65} We demonstrate that incorporating a lanthanide metal center into the azobenzene macrocyclic ligand scaffold **L-AzoH₂** uncovers a light-responsive system with tunable photoswitchable properties. Investigation of the photoresponsive behaviour of the **L-AzoH₂** macrocycle in chloroform showed that the free ligand does not exhibit any photoswitching properties under UV (320 nm) or visible (520 nm) light, with no observable changes in the absorption spectrum (Figure S42).

Figure 5. UV-vis absorption spectra of the NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ complex as a function of irradiation time, measured after a) 320 nm and b) 520 nm light irradiation. The inset photographs show the colour change of the macrocyclic complex upon a) UV and b) visible light exposure of the NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ complex in chloroform solution.

Photoresponsive behaviour of the NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ macrocyclic complex in a chloroform solution has shown that this system is a dual-responsive supramolecular assembly, as the photoswitching and photochromic properties were observed under UV light (320 nm) and visible light (520 nm). Upon irradiation of the NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ complex with 320 nm UV light, the absorbance of the π - π^* band at 403 nm gradually decreases, with a noticeable appearance of the n - π^* band as the intensity increases above 500 nm (Figure 5a).

These dependencies are typical of the *trans*-to-*cis* isomerization of azobenzene molecules.^{1, 66} Therefore, this observation is an obvious confirmation of the UV light-induced isomerization to the *cis*-conformation of the azobenzene moiety in the Nd³⁺ macrocyclic complex. The photostationary state for Nd³⁺ complex was reached after 3 h of irradiation, as indicated by intensity saturation of the band from the n - π^* transition (Figure 5a). We also revealed that the Nd³⁺ macrocyclic complex is sensitive to visible light irradiation, as exposure of the chloroform solution of neodymium complex to 520 nm light irradiation induces the same photochromic and photoisomerization behaviour. This is indicated by identical changes in the absorption spectrum profile (Figure 5b). The same rate of change from *trans* to *cis*-form under irradiation of the Nd³⁺ complex with visible light (4.00 mW/cm²) compared to UV light (1.68 mW/cm²) was observed after exposure to more intense light irradiation, as under the same conditions, the photoresponsive behaviour was practically invisible (for details, see section 1.1, in SI). This suggests greater sensitivity to far UV light exposure, as *trans*-to-*cis* photoisomerization is faster even at lower intensity of the incident UV light (Figure 5).

This led us to investigate whether L-AzoH₂ photoisomerization properties depend on the nature of the metal ion and protonation state of the ligand. Accordingly, we studied the influence of *s*-block metal ion - Na⁺ coordination, *d*-block metal ion - Cu²⁺ coordination in comparison with the *f*-electron cation - Nd³⁺. No evidence of the photoisomerization behaviour was observed for the [NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃ complex under exposure either to 320 nm or 520 nm light irradiation (Figure S43a). *In situ* deprotonation of ligand in sodium complex also did not change these results (Figure 43b). However, we observed that the copper complex (CuL-Azo), with ligand in its deprotonated form (for details, see Section 2.2.1. and SI Sections 1.4. and 1.5) exhibits reversible, photoswitchable behavior (Figure S43c), though no visible colour change of

investigated solution was noted. Finally, *in situ* preparation of [Nd(CF₃SO₃)₃-L-AzoH₂] without deprotonation of the phenolic lariat arms also leads to photoresponsive system, which is switched off after demetallation of system with excess trifluoroacetic acid (Figure S43d). This demonstrates that photoisomerization of the azobenzene moiety is dependent on both the protonation state of the ligand (see also Section 2.3.3.), but also electronic nature of the metal ion.

2.3.2. Isomerization at different wavelengths and stability studies of the *cis*-form

While the Nd³⁺ macrocycle responds efficiently to 320 nm and 520 nm light, its photoisomerization under other wavelengths in the 340-720 nm range is negligible (Figure S44a). A minor response appears in the 480-580 nm region, though significantly slower than the isomerization observed at 320 nm and 520 nm, where efficient isomerization to the *cis*-form occurs within 15 minutes (Figure S44a). These findings confirm that 320 nm and 520 nm are the most effective excitation wavelengths, prompting us to select 320 nm for detailed characterization due to its comparable efficacy and experimental consistency.

Based on these results, we focused our investigation on the stability of the photoinduced *cis*-isomer and its reversibility to the thermodynamically favoured *trans*-isomer. We examined the influence of various external stimuli known to trigger *cis*-to-*trans* back-isomerization – *i.e.* light, heat and dark storage – on the stability of the *cis*-isomer and recovery of the *trans*-form of the Nd³⁺ macrocyclic complex in solution. The *cis*-isomer remained highly stable at elevated temperature (40°C), showing no significant change in absorption intensity after 2 hours in chloroform solution (Figures 6a and S44b). Further temperature increase led to decomposition (Figure S44b). Visible light irradiation across 380-720 nm, failed to induce re-isomerization (Figure S45a). Dark storage in sealed quartz cuvette (wrapped in aluminium foil) also showed minimal recovery of the *trans* form after 24 hours, indicating high kinetic stability of the *cis* isomer (Figure S45b). After 14 days stored in the dark, the absorption band corresponding to the n - π^* transition at ~ 505 nm decreased by about 50%, while the π - π^* transition band at 403 nm recovered to 82% of its original *trans*-isomer intensity, indicating a very slow back-isomerization (Figure 6b and Figure S45b). These findings demonstrate the remarkable stability of the *cis*-form in the lanthanide macrocyclic complex, even under conditions typically efficient for induction of back-isomerization of azobenzene based compounds. Surprisingly, we observed that repeatedly aspirating the *cis*-rich solution of the Nd³⁺ complex with a glass Pasteur pipette led to a visible colour change from orange to yellow, suggesting a return to the *trans*-form. Indeed, after 5 minutes of repeated pipetting, approximately 90% of recovery of the *trans*-isomer was confirmed, regardless of whether the isomerization had originally been induced with 320 nm or 520 nm light (Figure 6c and Figure S46a, b).

2.3.3. Investigation of the underlying cause of the *cis*-to-*trans* re-isomerization mechanism

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Figure 6. Stability of the *cis*-isomer Nd^{3+} complex after 320 nm irradiation under varying conditions. a) effect of elevated temperature; b) stability during dark storage; c) manual agitation using a soda-lime-silicate glass pipette; d) UV-vis absorption spectra illustrating the response to various stimuli: 1-before irradiation, 2-after 20 minutes of 320 nm UV irradiation, 3 – after 320 nm UV irradiation followed by 15s shaking in a cuvette, 4-manual agitation with a plastic pipette (5 min), 5-manual agitation with a soda-lime-silicate glass pipette (5 min), 6-shaking with a crushed soda-lime-silicate glass (15 s), 7- manual stirring in a borosilicate or soda-lime-silicate vial (15 s), 8- manual stirring in a silanized borosilicate vial (5 min). Colour changes (inserted photographs) - legend for figures a, b, c: A-before irradiation, B-after irradiation at 320 nm, C-temperature exposure (a), storage in the dark (b), contact with a glass pipette (c); for figure d: A-before irradiation, B-after irradiation at 320 nm, after 320 nm irradiation and stirring in a borosilicate vial-X, or in soda-lime-silicate glass-Y. e) graphical representation of protonation and its effect on the photoresponsive behaviour of the macrocyclic lanthanide assemblies; for better demonstration of the process, phenolic arm is presented as non-coordinating, but solution and solid state studies demonstrate coordination in deprotonated form.

This unexpected observation prompted a series of control experiments to identify the underlying cause of the glass-induced re-isomerization. To test whether mechanical force was responsible, we subjected the solution to ultrasonic treatment. However, this led to decomposition of both *trans*- and *cis*-isomers of the complex (Figure S47a). Stirring the solution with a magnetic stir bar or shaking the quartz cuvette had no effect on the absorption spectra or colour of the solution (Figure 6d). The *cis*-isomer also remained stable in the presence of molecular oxygen (Figure S47b) and manual pipetting with a plastic pipette (Figure 6d). Furthermore, we demonstrated that transferring the orange *cis*-rich solution of the Nd^{3+} complex from a quartz cuvette into a borosilicate or soda-lime-silica vial and gently mixing for 15 seconds led to an immediate colour change to yellow, with full recovery of the *trans*-isomer absorption spectrum – consistent with results obtained via manual agitation using a glass pipette (Figure 6d). Similarly, adding crushed soda-lime-silicate glass (sourced from a pipette) to the *cis*-rich solution and shaking for 15 seconds also triggered immediate colour change and restoration of the original absorption profile, indicating that the glass surface itself is responsible for the back-isomerization (Figure 6d). To further investigate this, we added crushed soda-lime glass to the cuvette and left the sample undisturbed in the dark. A gradual return to the initial spectrum was observed after ~ 3 hours (Figure S48a). These experiments collectively support the conclusion that the re-isomerization is not mechanically induced but rather driven by surface interactions with glass.

Intriguingly, although glass has been shown to accelerate certain chemical reactions^{67,68} this effect has not been reported for photochemical processes—particularly not for azobenzene-based photoswitches. To probe the origin of the glass-mediated re-isomerization, we examined the effect of individual components of the glass. A large excess of NaCl (500x molar) did not induce re-isomerization over 24 h, excluding Na^+ leached from the glass as operative factor and suggesting that lack of photoresponsivity of $[\text{NaL-AzoH}_2]\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_3$ arises from metal identity. Silanized borosilicate slowed the recovery of the *trans* isomer from ca. 15 s to ca. 5 min (Figure 6d). Since silanization caps surface OH groups and suppresses formation of basic siloxide sites (SiO^-/M^+), this attenuation points to basic surface sites – not neutral Si-OH – as the active species. Consistently, adding even an excess of triphenyl silanol Ph_3SiOH to a *cis*-enriched solution produced no measurable effect (Figure S48b). Finally, excess of borax triggered immediate spectral recovery in few seconds, but led to slow decomposition of the complex over 24h (Figure S48c), consistent with basic character accelerating re-isomerization.

To assess whether protonation of phenoxide donors biases the photostationary state, we titrated a *cis*-rich $\text{NdL-AzoCF}_3\text{SO}_3$ complex with acetic acid and trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). Acetic acid produced a modest increase in the *cis* fraction, and re-isomerization to *trans* remained inducible by glass contact (Figure S48d). TFA increased the *cis* fraction at substoichiometric loadings, but once the acid exceeded ca. 0.5 equiv. it induced demetallation and the spectrum converged to that of the protonated ligand and *trans* isomer with loss of

reversibility (Figure S48e). In a *trans*-rich solution of NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃, TFA likewise generated *cis*, which triethylamine (TEA) cleanly reverted; several cycles were feasible provided the acid remained below the demetallation threshold (Figure S48f). Similar titration/irradiation cycle can be performed using glass instead of TEA (Figure S48g). To probe direct protonation, we assembled [Nd(CF₃SO₃)₃-L-AzoH₂] complex *in situ* and the solution immediately adopted the *cis* state, remained switchable by glass back to *trans*, and was again re-enriched to *cis* upon 320 nm irradiation. Storage in the dark for 2 days increased the *cis* fraction, again recoverable to *trans* by glass or TEA (Figures S48h,i). Spectra of *cis* generated by protonation and by 320 nm irradiation were indistinguishable within experimental uncertainty (Figure S48j). To complement the UV-Vis studies, we recorded ¹HNMR spectra on diamagnetic La³⁺ analogues (deprotonated LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃ and the *in situ* assembled [La(CF₃SO₃)₃-L-AzoH₂]). These observations are qualitative only, due to concentration-related aggregation and higher concentrations required for NMR ($\geq 10^{-3}$ M vs $\sim 10^{-5}$ M for UV-Vis). Irradiation and acid/base/glass treatments produced diagnostic, reversible changes in the azobenzene-adjacent aromatic region consistent with *trans/cis* interconversions and protonation/deprotonation (Figure S48k).

All data converge on protonation–deprotonation mechanism that influences the photostationary state. Mild protonation (acetic acid; substoichiometric TFA) biases the system toward *cis*, consistent with literature showing that protonation can facilitate azobenzene isomerization, in part by enabling azo–hydrazone tautomerism and altering excited-state pathways.⁶⁹ In our system, we hypothesize that protonation of the phenolic lariat arms promotes intramolecular proton transfer to the azo group, generating a hydrazone-type tautomer in which the N–N single bond lowers the rotational barrier (Figure 6e). This proposal is consistent with our observations that mild acid modestly enriches *cis* form, strong acid initially increases *cis* but ≥ 0.5 equiv. induces demetallation, and that base/glass (SiO⁻) restores the *trans*, deprotonated state. The *cis* state can likewise be generated photochemically (UV/Vis), whereas deprotonation restores the *trans* state. In this context, glass surfaces act as a benign heterogeneous base: interfacial SiO⁻ sites rapidly and reproducibly reintroduce the *trans* isomer without raising the bulk pH or degrading the complex (Figures 6d, S48d–k). Controls support this assignment: NaCl is inactive; silanized glass (fewer/basic sites) slows re-isomerization; a molecular silanol (Ph₃SiOH) has no effect; and borate/TEA also regenerate *trans* but can compromise stability with repeated cycles or higher loadings. Thus, glass functions as a solid–liquid “pH probe” and gentle base, enabling *cis/trans* recovery that is otherwise difficult to achieve with chemical reagents.

These results demonstrate that NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ functions as a dual photoswitch, undergoing efficient *trans*-to-*cis* isomerization under both UV and visible light – an uncommon feature in azobenzene-based systems.^{66, 70–74} Strikingly, the reverse *cis*-to-*trans* isomerization cannot be triggered by conventional stimuli such as heat (40°C), visible light (380–720 nm) or O₂⁷⁵ highlighting the high kinetic stability of the *cis*-form.

Remarkably, we discovered that contact with glass surfaces induces rapid recovery of the *trans*-isomer, revealing an unprecedented case of glass surface catalyzed re-isomerization. This behaviour was consistent across all synthesized lanthanide series (see Section 2.4), distinguishing our system from typical metal-azobenzene complexes and underscoring the critical role of ligand design and coordination environment in tuning the photoresponsive behaviour. Studies on related photoswitches are underway in our laboratory to ascertain if such an approach is compound specific, or can be of general use and was up to now overlooked in the literature.

2.4. The effect of lanthanide contraction on structural formation and photoisomerization properties: DFT studies

The photoisomerization behaviour of the free L-AzoH₂ ligand and the [NaL-AzoH₂]CF₃SO₃ and CuL-Azo complexes, compared with the NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ system, highlights the critical role of the lanthanide ion in enabling light-responsive functionality. Coordination of Ln³⁺ ions to the macrocyclic scaffold significantly alters the electronic environment, directly impacting absorption profiles and photoisomerization efficiency.^{76, 77,78, 79} Furthermore, structural variation across azobenzene-based metal complexes is known to affect their photochemical behaviour^{28, 80, 81} so we examined photoisomerization across the lanthanide series accordingly.

Figure 7. a) Schematic representation of how the lanthanide contraction phenomena influenced photoresponsive behaviour of specific groups of lanthanide-based macrocycles, b) computed rotational energy profiles for azobenzene isomerization in *syn*-LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃ (red circles) and *anti*-LuL-AzoCF₃SO₃ (black squares) complexes, showing relative energy (kcal/mol) as a function of dihedral rotation angle (°) around the N=N bond. Both profiles display distinct minima at *cis* (0°, 360°) and *trans* (180°) geometries, with the *trans*-form being the global minimum in each case.

The **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **PrL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **SmL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **EuL-AzoCF₃SO₃**, **GdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complexes exhibit photoisomerization behaviour similar to the **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complex. All undergo efficient *trans*-to-*cis* switching under both 320 nm and 520 nm irradiation, accompanied by pronounced changes in absorption spectra and visible photochromic effects. *Cis*-to-*trans* back-isomerization occurs rapidly via contact with glass surfaces, consistent across these early lanthanide complexes. Interestingly, they show greater sensitivity to UV light, with low-intensity 320 nm radiation yielding changes comparable to those induced by higher-intensity 520 nm light (Figures S49-S53). A shift in behaviour appears with **TbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complex, which shows reduced switching under UV but improves responsiveness to 520 nm visible light (Figure S54). For later lanthanides (**Dy³⁺** to **Lu³⁺**) 320 nm irradiation induces only minimal spectral changes, indicating suppressed photoisomerization under UV light (Figures S55a-S59a). The efficiency of photoswitchable behaviour in **LnL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complexes is closely governed by the ionic radius of the lanthanide, reflecting the influence of the lanthanide contraction. Based on this trend, the complexes can be broadly grouped into two categories. The first group (**La³⁺** to **Tb³⁺**) exhibits photoisomerization under both UV (320 nm) and visible (520 nm) light, with generally higher efficiency under higher energy light, even at lower intensities (Figure 7a - blue). Within this group, **Tb³⁺** shows a noticeable decline in responsiveness. The second group (**Dy³⁺** to **Lu³⁺**) displays little to no response to UV irradiation, though some photoisomerization persists under visible light (Figure 7a - green). Among the smallest ions (**Ho³⁺**, **Er³⁺**, **Yb³⁺**, **Lu³⁺**), the observed spectral changes and photochromism are minimal, underscoring a contraction-driven reduction in switching efficiency. Interestingly, it can be related to even smaller **Cu²⁺** ion, further showing a combined influence of the both the size and electronic nature of chosen cation on the photoresponsiveness. It remains plausible that metal-dependent electronic structure (e.g., heavy-atom/spin-orbit effects, ligand-field coupling, differences in nonradiative pathways) modulates the azobenzene excited-state landscape. Direct evidence would require time-resolved spectroscopy and electronic-structure calculations, which will be demonstrated in the forthcoming studies.

These distinct behaviours prompted further investigation into the kinetics of photoisomerization across the series. The macrocyclic complexes **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** were chosen as representatives of the early and late lanthanides, respectively. Notably, the **Yb³⁺** complex reached its photostationary state faster – after 105 minutes of irradiation – compared to 180 minutes for the **Nd³⁺** analogue (Figure S60, Figure 5a). The determined rate constant of the photoisomerization reaction for **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** (UV light -320 nm) and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** (visible light – 520 nm) were calculated as $k_{\text{Nd}} = 7.67 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_{\text{Yb}} = 4.10 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively, using a first-order kinetic equation (Figure S61). These values are lower than those typically reported for photoactive lanthanide complexes^{44-46, 48, 50, 51}. Comparison of the two reveals that the

syn-configured **Nd³⁺** complex switches more rapidly than the *anti*-configured **Yb³⁺** analogue.

To explore the structural origin of this behaviour and the influence of lanthanide contraction, we optimized the geometry of the **LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complex based on its solid-state structure and modeled the lutetium analogue by substituting **La³⁺** with **Lu³⁺**—which was not available in crystalline form. In both models, the coordinating triflate anion was included, yielding nine-coordinate structures (Figure S62). To validate the predicted structures, ¹HNMR chemical shifts were calculated for both conformers. The simulated spectra (Figure S63) matched well with the experimental data. In the **Lu³⁺** complex, methylene protons adjacent to the crown ether nitrogen atoms appeared at 3.2 and 4.6 ppm—consistent with the *anti*-conformation (compare with Figure 4). The deshielding of the aromatic protons further supported this assignment, with a *para*-positioned proton shifting downfield to 7.83 ppm.

This structural differentiation aligns with the DFT-calculated isomerization energy profiles. Since *trans/cis* photoisomerization of the azobenzene moiety was experimentally observed to be wavelength dependent the rotational barrier associated with the *trans/cis* isomerization was calculated. The same procedure was carried out for comparison with the **La³⁺** complex in the *syn*-conformation, which isomerizes both under 320 nm and 520 nm irradiation and the results are shown in Figure 7b. As observed and expected, the *trans*-isomer is more stable in both cases. Notably, the *anti*-configured **Lu³⁺** complex is thermodynamically less stable than the *syn*-structure by 8.4 kcal/mol, suggesting that its formation is kinetically driven by the smaller ionic radius of **Lu³⁺**. However, for the **La³⁺** complex, the rotational barrier enabling *cis*-to-*trans* conversion is 16.49 kcal/mol, whereas for the **Lu³⁺** complex, a higher barrier of 23.48 kcal/mol was calculated. The computed energy profiles reveal that the *anti*-**LuL-AzoCF₃SO₃** complex exhibits significantly higher isomerization barriers (~35 kcal/mol) than the *syn*-**LaL-AzoCF₃SO₃** analogue, consistent with the experimentally observed differences in photoisomerization efficiency. These findings collectively indicate that lanthanide contraction imposes rigidity and steric constraints around the azobenzene moiety, reducing conformational flexibility and suppressing photoisomerization.

2.5. Photoluminescence Studies and Luminescent Temperature Sensors

Based on the absorption characteristics, the luminescence properties of the sequence of lanthanide-based macrocyclic complexes were investigated in a solid-state form, using 370 nm excitation source. Note, the investigated solid materials have rigid structure, hence they do not undergo isomerization, and are stable under elevated temperature conditions, at least up to 220-270 °C (see the TGA - Figures S64-S75), making them suitable candidates for optical sensing applications.

Figure 8. a) Emission spectra of the **L-AzoH₂** macrocyclic ligand (black), and Ln-based macrocyclic complexes in solid-state form, under 370 nm excitation. b) Energy level diagram for the exemplary **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complexes (continuous lines – emission; dotted arrows – multiphonon relaxation; dashed arrows – intersystem crossing and energy transfer).

All of the lanthanide-based macrocyclic complexes show characteristic broad emission band of the **L-AzoH₂** macrocyclic ligand (see the spectra for the **L-AzoH₂** ligand and complexes in Figures S76 and S77), with a maximum at around 650 nm, as a result of the $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi$ transitions within the macrocyclic ligand (Figure 8a). Photoluminescence intensity of the macrocyclic complexes decreases when Ln³⁺ ions are incorporated into the complex, which is an evidence of ligand-to-metal energy transfer (LMET), from the **L-Azo** ligand to Ln³⁺ ions, as depicted in the energy level diagram in Figure 8b. First, the deprotonated **L-Azo** ligand is excited by UV light from the singlet S_0 to S_1 state, then the intersystem crossing (ISC) process occurs, and the energy is transferred to the triplet state of the ligand. Finally, ligand emission from the excited T_1 state can be observed, together with simultaneous LMET process, which results in the characteristic emission from Ln³⁺ ions.

Importantly, three of the Ln-based macrocyclic complexes show the characteristic for Ln³⁺ ions emission bands, *i.e.* **SmL-AzoCF₃SO₃** ($\lambda \approx 680$ nm), **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** ($\lambda \approx 890$ nm) and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** ($\lambda \approx 1000$ nm), as a result of the most efficient LMET process. These low-energy NIR-red emissions of the mentioned Ln³⁺ ions are observable, because these Ln³⁺ ions have their emitting states located below (in energy) the lowest excited triplet state of the ligand. Note, due to the same excitation mechanism for all complexes, and inefficient direct excitation of the Ln³⁺ in complexes (forbidden 4f-4f transitions), the excitation spectra for all compounds are almost identical and exhibit the same excitation band, as shown in the exemplary spectrum shown in Figure S76, which were used to estimate energies of S_1 and T_1 for the purpose of drawing the mentioned energy level diagram, indicating the possible radiative and nonradiative processes occurring in the studied system.

Following initial evaluation, two materials with the most intense lanthanide emissions, *i.e.* **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complexes were selected, and their emission properties were investigated under varied temperature conditions, from cryogenic to high temperature, *i.e.* from -180 to 160 °C (Figure 9). The first **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complex shows broad emission band in the visible (red) range, centred at ≈ 650 nm, associated with $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi$ transition from the macrocyclic part of the complex, as well as sharp emission bands from Nd³⁺ at around 890 nm (${}^4F_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{9/2}$)

and 1050 nm (${}^4F_{3/2} \rightarrow {}^4I_{11/2}$), accompanied with characteristics narrow peaks due to crystal-field split mJ sublevels (Figure 9a). Noteworthy, in this case, the influence of the Nd³⁺ absorption is also clearly visible in the form of intensity drops (due to Nd³⁺ reabsorption) at around 580, 670, 750 and 800 nm (${}^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^2G_{9/2}$, ${}^4F_{9/2}$, ${}^2G_{7/2}$ and ${}^4F_{5/2}$ Nd³⁺ transitions, respectively), biasing the expected round shape of the broad emission band ($\pi^* \rightarrow \pi$) from the organic component.

Figure 9. a, b) Emission spectra of the **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** (a) and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** (b) complexes as a function of temperature; c, d) the calculated LIR for the **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** (c) and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** (d) complexes; emission band centroids of Ln³⁺ for the **NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃** at ≈ 890 nm (e) and **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** at ≈ 1000 nm (f) complexes.

The gradual decrease of luminescence intensity of the deprotonated **L-Azo** ligand and Nd³⁺ as a function of temperature is a result of thermal quenching of emission in a non-radiative way (inset in Figure 9a).^{82, 83} A similar tendency was observed for the **YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃** macrocyclic complex in Figure 9b. However, the change of intensity for both bands (**L-Azo** and Ln³⁺) was not the same, hence we could calculate the luminescence intensity ratio (LIR) parameter for both macrocyclic complexes, which can work as thermometric parameter utilized in optical thermometry. The LIR between two emission bands of **L-Azo** ligand and Ln³⁺ ions (*i.e.* **L-Azo**/Nd³⁺ and **L-Azo**/Yb³⁺) change monotonously from around -70 to 110 °C for the Nd³⁺ complex, and from 20 to 160 °C for the Yb³⁺ complex, allowing their use as luminescent thermometers in the indicated operating temperature ranges (Figure 9c,d). Based on the calculated thermometric parameters we also calculated the relative thermal sensitivity (S_r) of the developed sensors using Eq. 1:

$$S_r = \frac{\partial LIR}{\partial T} \times \frac{1}{LIR} \times 100\% \text{ (Eq. 1)}$$

The S_r parameter for the NdL-AzoCF₃SO₃ complex reaches the maximum value of ≈ 0.89 %/°C at around 55°C (see inset in Figure 9c). Whereas, for the YbL-AzoCF₃SO₃ complex, the S_r parameter has the maximum value of ≈ 1.289 %/°C at the highest operating temperature, *i.e.* at 160°C (see inset in Figure 9d).

Another observed temperature-dependent spectroscopic effect is the spectral shift with temperature. In both materials spectral position of the L-Azo moiety emission band changes non-monotonously with temperature (data not shown), in contrast to the emission band centroids for the Nd³⁺ and Yb³⁺, which linearly change with temperature. Both emission bands, centred at $\lambda \approx 890$ nm for Nd³⁺ and at $\lambda \approx 1000$ nm for Yb³⁺, show linear blue-shift, with a rate $\Delta\lambda = -0.0151$ and -0.0381 nm/°C, respectively, caused by thermal expansion of the unit cell. Specifically, the observed spectral shift is due to the static contribution caused by the changes in the site geometry, which is occupied by the lanthanide ion in the crystal, as a result of lattice thermal expansion.^{82, 84} The observed spectral shifts, together with the discussed LIRs allow multi-parameter temperatures sensing in a relatively broad T -range. It is worth noting that due to severe quenching of Ln³⁺ luminescence by the solvent molecules, the characteristic emission bands originating from Ln³⁺ ions could be observed only in the solid-state form of the metal–organic complexes studied (see Figure S78 for comparison). Nonetheless, broad ligand centered emission overlaps the region typically used to excite the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ band and could possibly be the reason visible irradiation does not drive efficient *cis/trans* re-isomerization. While metal coordination, aggregation effects and matrix rigidity may also play a role in this, a definitive mechanism will require time-resolved and solvent-dependent studies beyond the present scope.

3. Conclusions

We report the development of a new class of photoswitchable lanthanide-based macrocyclic complexes, where *trans*-to-*cis* isomerization is induced by light and reversed through an unprecedented glass-surface-mediated mechanism. Structural and spectroscopic studies across the LnL-AzoCF₃SO₃ series revealed two distinct structural regimes. Complexes from La³⁺ to Tb³⁺ and Er³⁺ adopt a consistent nine-coordinate geometry comprising donor atoms from the diazacrown ether, azobenzene moiety and a monodentate triflate anion. Despite this apparent structural consistency, ¹HNMR and DFT studies identified a conformational shift from a *syn*- to *anti*-arrangement as the lanthanide series progresses - correlated with increased ligand rigidity and higher isomerization barriers.

All synthesized Ln-complexes display light-responsive behaviour, with most undergoing reversible *trans*-to-*cis* photoisomerization in solution under UV and/or visible light irradiation. Switching efficiency depends on the nature of the lanthanide ion and its electronic structure, with suppression

observed in certain cases, particularly for smaller lanthanides, aligning with computational findings and highlighting the impact of lanthanide contraction on the photoswitching dynamics. Notably, the reverse *cis/trans* isomerization proved unresponsive to conventional triggers such as heat, visible light, or oxygen, but occurring rapidly under contact with the glass surface. This unusual recovery combined with high stability of the *cis*-isomer introduces an unprecedented case of glass driven re-isomerization of the diazobenzene photoswitches, and can be explained on the basis of protonation/deprotonation behaviour.

In addition to the photoresponsive solution behaviour, the solid-state luminescence properties of the complexes were also investigated, with Nd³⁺ and Yb³⁺ complexes exhibiting promising thermosensitive emissions. These systems function as dual VIS/NIR luminescent thermometers, based on LIR and band shifts, representing the first example of such dual photoswitchable and luminescent macrocyclic systems. The combined study of isomerization and emission behaviour under light irradiation underscores the potential of these macrocycles as multi-stimuli-responsive lanthanide platforms. This work provides new insight into the interplay between macrocyclic conformation, metal ion size and external stimuli, offering a valuable design strategy for future development of functional lanthanide-based supramolecular materials.

Author Contributions

Dominika Prętko: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing–review & editing; Dawid Marcinkowski: Formal analysis, Resources; Nahir Vadra: Investigation, Resources; Przemysław Woźny: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft; Marcin Runowski: Conceptualization, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Resources; Maciej Kubicki: Data curation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing–original draft; Violetta Patroniak: Supervision, Resources, Visualization, Writing – review & editing; Giuseppe Consiglio: Formal Analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing; Giuseppe Forte: Formal Analysis, Methodology, Writing – review & editing; Adam Gorczyński: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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